

THE COMMON KINGFISHER (*ALCEDO ATTHIS*): AN EXCEPTIONAL FIRST RECORD FOR THE WEST INDIES AND THE WESTERN HEMISPHERE

Yaroddy Rodríguez¹, Orlando H. Garrido², James W. Wiley^{3,5}, & Arturo Kirkconnell⁴

¹Calle H % 243 No. 370, reparto Lugones, Ciego de Ávila, Cuba.

²Calle 60 No. 1706, entre 17 y 19, Marianao 13 (Playa), La Habana, Cuba.

³USGS, Maryland Cooperative Fish and Wildlife Research Unit, 1120 Trigg Hall, University of Maryland Eastern Shore, Princess Anne, MD 21853, USA. *E-mail*: jwwiley@mail.umes.edu

⁴Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, Obispo 61, Habana Vieja, La Habana, Cuba.

El Martín Pescador Común (*Alcedo atthis*): primer registro excepcional para las Antillas y el Hemisferio Occidental.

Key words: *Alcedo atthis*, Common Kingfisher, Cuba, record.

On 20 April 2003, Rodríguez obtained a Common Kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*) within 2 km of Palo Alto, east of Júcaro, and south of Ciego de Ávila, Cuba. Three boys had killed the kingfisher with sling shots after a long pursuit through the local mangroves. Rodríguez prepared the specimen as a study skin, which now is in his private collection. The bird was an adult, based on the abundant abdominal and breast fat, as well as plumage characteristics. Measurements taken included: total length: 174 mm, wing chord: 71 mm, bill length: 36 mm, tarsus length: 24 mm, and tail length: 27 mm.

The Common Kingfisher is widely distributed throughout Palearctic and Oriental regions, to New Guinea and the Solomons Islands (Clements 1978, Bruun & Singer

1980, Fry & Fry 1992). The specimen from Cuba constitutes the first record from the West Indies and, moreover, the Western Hemisphere. We do not know how it reached the Cuban coast, although we do not believe it was by human introduction.

REFERENCES

- Bruun, B., & A. Singer. 1980. Guía de las aves de España y de Europa. Ediciones Omega, S.A. Casanova, Barcelona, Spain.
- Clements, J. F. 1978. Birds of the world: a check list. Two Continents Publishing Group, LTD, New York, New York.
- Fry, C. H., & K. Fry. 1992. Kingfishers, bee-eaters, & rollers. Princeton Univ. Press, Princeton, New Jersey.

⁵Corresponding author e-mail: jwwiley@mail.umes.edu

Accepted 29 September 2004.

